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NEWS

Visual Astronomy Display: March 2015

Katie Frey Updated on August 24, 2022 [Leave a Comment](#)

Visual Astronomy Display for March 2015

Highlights...

- The Solar Dynamics Observatory celebrates its 5th anniversary with a **time-lapse video of the sun that captures one frame every 8 hours for nearly 5 years**;
- NASA share's a video about the wrap up of **Curiosity's "walkabout" exploration** of the Pahrump Hills on Mars;
- Astronaut Col. **Chris Hadfield shares what it is like to see Earth from orbit** in a video from Veritasium;
- Ever **wondered what the "dark side" of the Moon looks like?** NASA share's a computer generated video based on satellite data from the far side of the Moon;
- The team at the Hubble Space Telescope shared a video that **journeys through the life and times of astronomer Edwin Hubble**, whose name graces one of the most significant scientific instruments ever built; and
- NASA satellite CALIPSO tracks how much **dust travels from the Sahara desert in Africa over Atlantic Ocean** to settle in the Amazon rainforest of South America.

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Katie Frey leads the development of the Unified Astronomy Thesaurus, a community supported linked data vocabulary for sorting, filtering, and exploring astronomical literature, data sets, images, etc.

About Katie Frey

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